

An Overview of Trauma-Informed Education and Counselling in Nigeria

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Abstract

This work is an opinion paper on trauma informed education and counselling. The manuscript looked at the historical development of guidance and counselling in western world and Nigeria inclusive. It also revealed that counselling practices in Nigeria involves a relationship between the professional counsellors and counsellee or client or a group of clients in an attempt to help him or her make adequate choices and adjusts his or her life. Historical development of guidance and counselling; trauma informed education in Nigeria; trauma informed counselling interventions for Internally Displace Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria; trauma informed counselling and menace of drug use or addiction in Nigerian schools; trauma-informed counselling and mental health; and the ethical standards for the relationship were stated. Thus, trauma informed education in Nigeria (which calls for counselling intervention to prevent the problem or crisis from further occurrence) was discussed extensively. These include trauma informed counselling interventions for internally displace persons (IDPs) in Nigeria; trauma informed counselling and menace of drug use/addiction in Nigerian schools; and trauma-informed counselling and mental health.

Keywords: Trauma, informed education, counselling, Nigeria

Introduction

Trauma is an adverse experience that compromises an individual's sense of being safe in relationships and in the world around them, and can significantly inhibit both self-regulatory and relational capacities required for successful learning (Brunzell, 2021). In recent years, there has been growing awareness of the widespread prevalence of trauma experiences. Trauma is a physiological and psychological experience where an individual experiences overwhelming fear for their life either literally or figuratively (Van der Kolk, 2014). One can figuratively fear for their life through witnessing a violent act or accident without being directly involved, such as witnessing a car accident where a person dies. After a traumatic event or a series of events, it is normal for one to experience fear, stress and a heightened state of alertness (Shonkoff et al 2012). With simple trauma, these experiences tend to be brief, often occurring only once, however, complex relational trauma occurs over time. The effects of complex relational trauma are profound and multiple. Trauma informed education helps teachers understand the impacts of trauma and suggests proactive strategies to position the school itself as a predictable milieu for healing and growth. Trauma informed education practices is a mindset, an acceptance of diversity, including background, knowledge, skills and life experiences and an understanding that some of those life experiences may be varied. Trauma informed education can help create an equitable learning environment supportive of all learners (Najjaar, 2023).

An Overview of Trauma-Informed ... (Anake, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10687767>

Trauma informed education plays education is played out as foremost in ensuring that the policy of education and goals are actualized in its citizenry. Thus, trauma informed education and counselling is geared towards ensuring mental wellbeing, drug use and addiction, skills and ethics and counselling intervention may perhaps address and arrest the overwhelming flood of traumatized individuals in the institutions of learning. Trauma informed counsellors are open and honest with clients. They make sure that they are education and up-to-date with clients who have experienced trauma. They are also aware of the unique cultural considerations that each client experiences (Marschall, 2023).

Historical development of guidance and counselling in the western world

Formal counselling started in the western countries as a philanthropically outreach to children who were maltreated in factories as factory workers. Jersey B. Ravis in 1898-1907, on philosophical and moral grounds, did not like child labour. He gathered children in the stress and talked to them on how they were used for selfish interest. He saw the practice as an extreme situation of child abuse and abuse of their fundamental human rights. He said that they were used as slaves by the employers to work for them at the expense of schooling (Enya & Obot, 2021).

In the same vein in 1900 in Boston Frank Parson also showed concern about child abuse. He was dissatisfied with how children were being handled by industrialists. Between 1900-1960, many people had become involved in the in and out of school activity. In Michigan schools, principals organized the children and addressed them in a forum that resembled a career seminar. They even taught career education in their English lesson.

In 1910, efforts were collated and put in a journal called National vocational guidance Association (NVGA). In 1915, a conference was organized in Boston City involving all pioneer guidance workers. Later, emphasis shifted from children to all who had to work in both public and private enterprises. In 1952, American Personnel and Guidance Association (APGA) was formed to replace the former body. In 1983-85, took a name American Association for Counselling and Development (AACD). Under this name they become a larger organization in behavioural sciences that had to do with human organization. This expansion was facilitated by factors such as philanthropy, personality awareness, mental hygiene movement and religious organizations that gave the association enough challenges.

In line with the formal guidance started in Nigeria in 1959 among some religious sisters from Ireland in St. Theresa's College, Oke Afa, Ibadan. The Rev. Sisters organized careers' week activities and invited community members to advise and direct them on the placement of their final year students. The advisers were not guidance counsellors, but they were experience in job selection and placement of secondary school graduates. This group formed themselves into a group called Ibadan Careers Council. They further organized workshops for career mistresses and masters on vocational guidance in Ibadan. Similarly, at the Comprehensive High School, Aiyetoro, guidance programme commenced with the use of American Standardized Tests by a Harvard (USAID) (Denga, 2012). These Harvard USAID sponsored counselors at Aiyetoro really started the guidance programme in Nigeria. They trained some Nigerian counselors in the task of implementing vocational and educational counselling. In 1974, the idea of school guidance had spread to all parts of Nigeria.

Today, the professional body is known as the Counselling Association of Nigeria (CASSON). The second and third national development plans of 1970 and 1972, respectively backed up the innovation of guidance and counselling and it growth rapidly in Nigeria. Counselling practice in Nigeria involves a relationship between the professional counsellors and counsellee or client or a group of clients in an attempt to help him or her make adequate choices and adjusts his or her life. The ethical standards for this type of relationship are as follows: 1) to respect the integrity of the individual; 2) to keep counselling information confidential; 3) make the counsellee to be aware of the purpose, goals, techniques and rules of the procedure and limitations of the counselling activities; 4) make referrals to other professionals or specialists you feel can assist the counsellee; and 5) where there is an evaluative relationship between professional and client, counselling is not necessary or may not be successful. Based on this historical origin of guidance and counselling in Nigeria, trauma informed education which calls for counselling intervention to prevent the problem or crisis from further occurrence.

Trauma informed education (TIE) in Nigeria

Life holds much in stuck for all who are born into the world. Unfortunately, not all who are born into this world would go through life's channels without facing adversities. Adversity constitutes life challenges that overwhelm individual(s), but coping skills and ability to overcome these challenges when not possessed by those who needs them; it becomes a traumatic situation. Trauma as it were is used to describe a gamut of stressful event that invitro children pass through (children and young adults up to the age of 24 years. Trauma can include collection of adversities in its entirety that

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afflicts a child directly and indirectly. These assortments of experience include physical abuses such as kicking, slapping, hitting, spitting on and multiple others. These may lead them to emotional trauma such as withdrawal of affections, neglects, snide remarks, negative confrontations, shouting and verbal missiles; these abuses are related to familial experiences among household members and close relationship. Abuses sweep across the sexual and non-sexual approaches. Such abuse on a child and young adults leaves them paralyzed throughout life time. Trauma can occur at variant levels and at different stages of a child's life her or she may experience trauma. Examples of such trauma are parental separation, domestic violence, parental drug abuse, financial hardship and mental instructionalization of parents.

Birtwek (2017) adjoined that trauma is an overwhelming experience that undermines a person's belief in himself and the world. In a same light, Samhsa (2014) defined trauma as the various ways an individual had been exposed to various experiences that engulfs both the internal and external coping resources available to them, submerging them into a sense of extreme threat that inflict negative effects on their function and wellbeing. The American Psychological Association (2022) flashed out that trauma may have concocted as a result of various adversities, which may be natural or man-made disasters. Furthermore, Bellis et al (2014) brought forward that at least one type of adversity had occurred to a person prior to 18 years. The traumatic experience underpins the potentials of the person. On this basis, education plays a key role in ensuring that trauma informed education is played out as foremost in ensuring that the policy of education and goals are actualized in its citizenry. Thus, trauma informed education, counselling towards ensuring mental wellbeing, drug use and addiction, skills and ethics and counselling intervention may perhaps address and arrest the overwhelming flood of traumatized individuals in the institutions of learning in Nigeria. There is an urgent need to understand the implication of trauma on the educational system and how trauma informed education can unveil the menace of poor wellbeing, drug intake habits and other associated symptoms of traumatized lives. The impacts of trauma in the lives of traumatized adolescents leave nothing to be desired. It is linked to fear, detrimental health, increase inn behavioural disorders, neurotism and its associated factors, high risk sexual behaviours, absenteeism from classes, gangterism, long term health disorders, truncated relationship, job instabilities, unemployment, environmental unrest (armed robbery, cultism among others) (DuPaul et al, 2014).

Ne-Meroff (2015) has positioned that early childhood trauma such as neglect, abuse and isolation, imparts the brain. As admitted in studies, Ne-Meroff initiated that normal brain development is disrupted when an individual experiences trauma to the point that a clear distinction is made between biological age and physical development. Likewise, (Dye (2018) pointed out that the brain functioning is abruptly disrupted by aversions experiences. He noted that the brain including the brain stem (regulating stress and metabolism), the midbrain (responsible for sensory motor control, sleep and appetite), the limbic system (regulates emotions, attachment, affiliation, language and reasoning). Dye (2018) further enumerated that experiencing trauma may result in depression, anxiety, anger and aggression.

Cognition is the bedrock of knowledge while traumatic symptoms are physiologically and neurologically implicated. The impact of trauma on children and young adult or adolescents impairs learning and triggers assorted educational problems in the individual(s) and the national institutions as a whole. The uneducated populace, poorly educated populace and traumatized persons is of grave concern to the educational institutions and reform of the nation(s). This gives room to questioning on: What can be done to alleviate these maladies, what are the steps to be taken to remedy traumatized lives, where do we go from here as educationists? How do we help these adolescent students from traumatized background and how do we as institution implement a system of trauma informed education organization. The educational institution is perturbed by the numerous undergraduates, graduates and postgraduates' students who have had and are still experiencing trauma in the midst of our educational system. Thus, can trauma-informed counselling skills and ethics have required by counselor trainees. A counsellor believes that you have answers within you and together you can find them. Counselling is not an imposition on the client but a willing relationship by the client to seek for help. Like any other professions, there are boundaries and parameters for practice. In maintaining appropriate boundaries for the counselor, trainee and client, so that they do not enter inappropriate relationship with client or take physical, emotional, sexual psychological or financial advantage of clients. This brings to bear the issue of ethical standard and practice. The guidelines are based on the code of ethics (2004) as approved by the American Counselling Association (ACA). The private nature of counselling session leaves a gap for unsuspected practice, thus the need of code of ethics that identifies principles and behaviour that are in harmony and congruent with the mission and purpose of counselling based on moral precepts and professional behaviour. This calls for the need of adopting counselling skills for maintaining compassionate regard for the client by demonstrating a way of being courteous, tactful, sensitive, accepting, empathetic and nonjudgmental. Therefore counselor, psychotherapist, trainees undertaking role(s) of counselling skills must be conversant with the need of preventing further traumatic disorder among client or adolescents in school.

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Similarly, professional code of ethics provides a substantive basis for decision making. To educate counselor trainees about sound ethical conduct, provide mechanism for professional accountability for improving practice. To safeguard the welfare of the client by providing what is in their best interest. Also provide an objective standard of evaluation of specific traumatic areas of potential conflict. Also provide template that professional can take to resolve complex issues in a rational manner. Provide guidance in what is expected to professional and what is accepted responses to problem which arise. All these with clarity of purpose help the adolescent(s) with problem to resolve issues and adjust positively. Trauma informed counselling skills and ethics in addressing and proffering services to students faced with problems of financial hardship, family problems, issues of rape, poor academic performance, poor accommodation, school and community unrest and unhealthy relationships and unemployment. All these traumatic situations call for the need of counselling services and help to put the individual back on track. Also to overhauled the educational system and implement policy that provide opportunity for a wholistic development of the child in school and society.

Trauma informed counselling interventions for Internal Displace Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria

An individual's (or children's) physical, mental and emotional wellbeing supports their overall development and learning which helps them to grow and learn optimally while building skills required to attained their full potential (Childhood Education International, 2021). Along the course of life's journey, something precarious happened which affect their physical health and wellbeing. This may lead to poor access to food, shelter, poor sanitary and unsafe living conditions, no access to places to play and exercise, pre-primary education, or higher education. Thus, early exposure to insensitive, maltreatment and neglectful caretaking can affect a child's sense of safety and security which is essential to the development of a secure person. In line with this, Fonagy (2014) affirmed that the exposure to trauma in early childhood, namely abuse or neglect has the potentials to derail a parent's capacity to attend to their children, especially in moment of distress, and has been found to impact their children's attachment style and educational outcome. Luberman, Ghosh and Van (2015) vent that cues children given when needing their caretaking attention can be misinterpreted by parents with a history of child abuse or neglect as threatening and overwhelming and can lead to perceptual distortions that inhibits the child's need from being met and the parents' capacity to respond abruptly. Trauma informed counselling interventions becomes very crucial to address the neurological, physiological and psychological disruption that ultimately impacts on the parents and young person's education and school related outcomes in IDPs. The counselor adopting the theory of Bowlby attachment and Ellis rational emotive behaviour therapy, should advise parents and caregivers in IDPs to be more loving, caring and accepting their adolescents or children with no personal regards. Also, professional should help victims in IDPs to start rethinking positively about their life experiences; replacing negative thoughts with positive thinking and reasoning.

The counselling also in collaboration with government, social health workers, philanthropists, policy makers should help make adequate provision for shelter, food, safety, security, education and create a sense of belongingness among victims. Also create in them a sense of safe, stable and nurturing relationship with community members, prevent violence and improve mental health and support. Chafoules et al (2019) posited that schools have the opportunity to create safe and supportive environment by applying trauma aware assumptions in their day to day practice. This informed educators to understand and draw from trauma-aware pedagogies and help teachers to cater for the behavioural and learning needs of trauma affected children or adolescents in a meaningful way, creating an environment that promotes inclusion of healing and personal growth.

Trauma informed counselling and menace of drug use/addiction in Nigeria school

The fastest and easiest road to teenage child's ruin is drug use and addiction. Any chemical substance whether of natural and synthetic origin, which is used to alter perception, mood or other psychological states, affects the individual. Adolescents do not believe the effect of drug used. Many are simply unaware of the dangers and damages to health, which may lead to disorders such as depression and memory loss. Bergholz, Stafford and D'Andrea (2016) observed that students who struggle to adhere to rules, inability to handle pressure, inability to form connection with team-mates, exhibit aggressiveness, defiance, social withdrawal, unable to regulate their emotions and symptomatic trauma. Ellison, Watton-Fisette and Eckert (2019) ascertained that individual nature of traumatic experiences may be individualized, depending on maturation, intelligence, social environment, family support, school support, nature of the experience and relationship with perpetrators of drug used. An adolescent who is traumatized with drug use and addiction is one at risk; they are frustrated, hostile and aggressive. They exhibit temper tantrums and destructiveness. Based on this, counselors create awareness and

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sensitization programmes on the influence of drug use and addiction and its consequences on the health and mental imbalance of an individual. Parents should check their life style in the use of drug and even being addicted, to guide their upbringing from being exemplary of their parents. An addicted adolescent is one at risk, parent should find it necessary to socialized their adolescents to common forms and values of the home, school and society.

Trauma-informed counselling and mental health

Childhood Education International (2021) explained that traumatic and stressful childhood experiences can place children at great risk for emotional and mental health challenges. In schools, trauma-informed counselling and mental health as required administrative byelaw and support practices, traumatic sensitive classroom practice, negative response to behaviour, policy and procedure changes, teacher and staff professional development and strong cross system collaboration among school staff and mental health professionals (Oehlberg, 2020). Trauma can have long-term effects on the person's well-being. If symptoms persist and do not decrease in severity, it can indicate that the trauma has developed into a mental health disorder called post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD).

Finally, trauma informed education, mental wellbeing, counselling skills and ethics, counselling interventions, drug use and addiction and mental health; to help alleviate the negative impact of adverse childhood experiences leading to trauma as resilience that can help the counselors, educators and parents protect children from the detrimental effects of traumatized experiences; such as safe, stable and nurturing relationships and improve self-reliance and mental health of individuals.

Types of traumas

There are several types of trauma, including: 1) Acute trauma – This results from a single stressful or dangerous event; 2) Chronic trauma – This results from repeated and prolonged exposure to highly stressful events. Examples include cases of child abuse, bullying, or domestic violence; 3) Complex trauma – This results from exposure to multiple traumatic events; 4) Secondary trauma, or vicarious trauma – With this form of trauma, a person develops trauma symptoms from close contact with someone who has experienced a traumatic event. Family members, mental health professionals, and others who care for those who have experienced a traumatic event are at risk of vicarious trauma.

Treatment of Trauma

Several treatments can help people with trauma to cope with their symptoms and improve their quality of life. This can be treated through therapy.

- a. **Therapy:** Therapy is a first-line treatment for trauma. Ideally, an individual will work with a trauma informed or trauma focused therapist. Types of therapy a person with trauma could benefit from include:
 1. Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) helps people to change their thought patterns in order to influence their behaviors and emotions.
 2. Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing: Eye movement desensitization and reprocessing (EMDR) is another common trauma therapy. During EMDR, individuals briefly relive specific traumatic experiences while the therapist directs their eye movements. EMDR aims to help people process and integrate traumatic memories.
 3. Somatic therapies: Some therapists use somatic or body-based techniques to help the mind and the body process trauma. These therapies include: i) Somatic experiencing – This approach involves a therapist helping a person to relive traumatic memories in a safe space; ii) Sensorimotor psychotherapy – This type of therapy combines psychotherapy with body-based techniques to turn traumatic memories into sources of strength; iii) Acupoint stimulation – This involves a practitioner applying pressure to specific points on the body, which induces a state of relaxation; and iv) Touch therapies – Other touch therapies include Reiki, healing touch, and therapeutic touch therapy.
- b. **Medications:** Trauma can also be managed through medication. Medication alone cannot cure trauma or PTSD, but it can help a person manage symptoms such as anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbances. A person should talk to their doctor about their options.
- c. **Self-care:** Practicing self-care can help individuals to cope with the emotional, psychological, and physical symptoms of trauma. Examples of self-care for trauma include: 1) Exercise: Trauma can activate the body's fight-or-flight response. Exercise may help mitigate some of these effects. Individuals can aim to exercise for at least 30 minutes a day on most days of the week; 2) Mindfulness: Mindful breathing and other mindfulness-based exercises can ground people in the

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present, which can stop them from reliving the traumatic event; 3) Connection with others: Withdrawal from others is a common symptom of trauma. However, connecting with friends and family is important.

- d. **A balanced lifestyle:** A person with trauma may find it difficult to relax or to sleep well. However, sleep, relaxation, and diet all play a role in mental health. If possible, a person should try to: sleep for 7–9 hours a night; eat a balanced diet; avoid alcohol and drugs; and relieve stress with mindful or enjoyable activities.

Conclusions

Trauma informed counselling allows you to validate your emotions, assess your current coping mechanisms (which may for example involve unhealthy habits such as substance abuse), help to make sense of what has happened in your life, move away from avoidance and suppressive behaviours, understand, recognize and integrate self in traumatic situations. Hence trauma counselling (also referred to as trauma debriefing) is essentially the healing process of which assists an individual(s) to deal with symptoms that you are struck with after a traumatic event. Trauma counselling helps individual(s) to identify and come to terms with feelings and emotions they may experience during and after a traumatic event. These emotions may vary from individual to individuals. As well as helping with identifying the causes of stress, counselling can also help to understand the role that one's thoughts play in increasing stress level. The process of counselling also provides employees with a sounding board to talk about issues that they are experiencing. Counselling can help improve mood, treat mental illness, reduce medical illness, improve communication and relationships and promote self-esteem and resilience. Furthermore, counselling in trauma informed education, is known as one of the greatest helping professions on earth, yet many people remain perplexed about its true meaning, purpose and intention. Most likely, the practice of offering counselling to others has always occurred in some fashion within human society – humans are relational beings experience a range of emotions and have an innate desire to avoid suffering and live abundant lives. Today, one in five American adults, has mental health condition and research shows that these conditions can be effectively treated (Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, 2018). Not only can counselling treat mental health conditions, it can also help individuals, groups, organizations and society optimizes wellbeing.

Accordingly, millions of people have experienced the benefits of counselling. Counselling is a specific mental health discipline that includes aspects of guidance and psychotherapy. It focuses on a wellness model aimed at improving the quality of life and involves both counsellor and client in collaboration. Psychotherapy and other counselling techniques help individuals explore moods and behaviours, provide fresh perspectives and offer a better understanding of emotions. Trauma is the physical emotional and psychological response when a person experiences high levels of fear or stress without having the chance to escape or mobilize (more away). It is a stress response that remains frozen in time within the person. A good trauma therapist can provide a grounded presence where individual(s) can begin to explore their trauma while feeling safe, listened to and held. This helps the effected person learn how to come down from hyperarousal and help to be grounded in the here-and-now experience. Moreso, trauma informed education and counselling and mental health to help a trauma survivor to recognize their resources and skills and to build on these. Also, survivor of traumatic situation learns how to regulate emotions and feel safer in the here-and-now. Thus, working with a trauma therapist can help individuals to understand trauma symptoms and to start working through their experiences.

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